

ERRATUM

Due to a regretful event of crossed wires in our small and friendly editorial team and my losing a keen eye toward a hectic end of the year, two articles published in Volume 54 (2025) of the *Israel Journal of Entomology* received overlapping pagination: Payra *et al.* (2025) and Volynkin & Černý (2025).

The latter is to retain its original pagination

Volynkin, A.V. & Černý, K. 2025. Taxonomic review of the genus *Mithuna* Moore (Lepidoptera: Erebidae: Arctiinae: Lithosiini), with descriptions of two new genera and seventeen new species. *Israel Journal of Entomology* **54**: 113–165.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17927846>

<urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:1BC21B27-5EE9-4BDB-9E74-A6AA1DDD10E5>

whereas the former may (and should) be cited as

Payra, A., Kuni, N. & Koparde, P. 2025. First instance of non-sexual cannibalism in *Plexippus paykulli* (Audouin) (Araneae: Salticidae) in India. *Israel Journal of Entomology* **54**: [113]–[115]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787293>

<urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:290CDD94-02CD-4042-8F37-574ED9826FFE>

The corresponding metadata of Payra *et al.* (2025) in the Zenodo archive and ZooBank have been updated, but neither the article page on the journal Website nor the published PDF file can be amended without breaking the integrity of cross-linking.

I profoundly apologize to the respected authors and our valued readers for this most unfortunate oversight and for any inconvenience it may cause.

Chief Editor

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